

The Lived-Experiences of SHS Students using Edmodo Application as a Language Assessment Tool

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Abstract

This study materialized with the purpose of determining the lived experiences of students towards the use of the Edmodo Application as a language tool. Being qualitative in nature, the interview as the data gathering tool was utilized with an audio recorder. Participants of the study were twenty-three Grade 12 students taking Computer System Servicing who experienced the use of the Edmodo Application at Ambuklao National High School (formerly Tublay School of Home Industries-Annex) Ambuklao, Bokod, Benguet. Data elicited were transcribed verbatim, confirmed by the participants, coded and categorized, and thematically coded accordingly.

Through the use of the interview guide, data were generated from which significant statements were drawn and identified, and it was categorized into similar scenarios to form themes. The phenomenon was then depicted by the researcher through the surfaced themes, namely: Neophyte's Views, Amateur's Views, and Language Learning Specs in the Edmodo App.

Based on the conclusion, the following are recommended: 1) School administrators are highly encouraged to adapt the online assessment tool and introduce it to teachers to apply the important insights on the potential opportunities of technologies in facilitating higher-order thinking content. 2) Teachers who would like to level up their traditional classrooms in the current scenario to create a responsible learning environment for the students should make online activities livelier. 3) Educators need to recognize and emphasize the value of embedding assessment within learning processes and the value of assessing products as well as processes of learning. 4) Assuming continuous growth of social networks, inform the school administrator to come up with a fast internet connection in the computer laboratory room for desirable educational outcomes.

Keywords: *Edmodo; Assessment Tool*

1. Introduction

Technology nowadays plays a crucial role for every individual. It makes life easier and faster. For educational fields, it helps the learners to level up in learning. It would even help them prepare for their future.

In today's generation, a fast-paced, technology-driven era of advancement and development, technology has transformed educational environments and introduced new approaches to learning and teaching attitudes. Belland (2009) defined technology integration as "the sustainable and persistent change in the social system of K-12 schools caused by the adoption of technology to help students construct knowledge (like research and analyze information to solve problems)".

The educational process, as described by Prasad et al. (2012), requires more than traditional teacher-student roles; these roles are eventually changing. A student becomes a learner, and his/her role is to become an active thinker rather than a passive listener, while a teacher becomes a guide to lead learners to relevant information as well as define the needs and expectations of students, and help them find and use knowledge or information. Computer techniques have developed to a high level, including both software and hardware. The application of computers in education has appeared in most fields.

1.1 Research Objectives

1. To know the general reactions or perceptions of the Grade 12 Senior High School Students on the Edmodo Application.
2. To know the respondents' views on the use of Edmodo as a language tool in language.
3. To know the significant uses of Edmodo in language assessment.

2. Methods

2.1 Research Design

This study used a phenomenology approach.

2.2 Participants

A total of 23 senior high school students from Ambuklao National High School.

2.3 Data Collection Instruments

- Structured Interviews
- Focus Group Discussion

2.4 Procedure

A one-on-one interview was conducted and transcribed from the recording, followed by a focus group discussion (FGD).

2.5 Data Analysis

Interview responses were transcribed and analyzed thematically.

3. Results

3.1 Findings

Three main themes emerged from the interviews:

1. The Neophyte's Views
2. The Amateur's Views
3. Language Learning Specs in Edmodo Application.

4. Discussion

The current study approved that the Edmodo Application was overall successful for almost all CSS students in their language assessment. It became pleasurable, appreciated, and interesting.

The first problem is about the reaction or perceptions of the respondents when the Edmodo Application was first introduced.

1. The Inquirers: whose most of the questions they've asked were anchored on the know-hows of the online application. Various questions came to mind about its usage. The respondents claimed that they became inquisitive at first about the application.

2. The Optimists' Views: viewers who had the guts to think positively, even though they were not aware in the first place of what could be that thing they are about to use. These respondents were described as very active. They believe that there is enjoyment when using this new type of assessment tool at school.

3. The Pessimists: those who had negative impressions when the application was introduced. They thought of the application as different from the usual way of assessing, and that it could be very difficult on their level.

4. The Wanderers: even immersion was foreseen upon introduction, some respondents are really innocent with the use of the application, or rather, the technology. From the respondents' confessions, most of them are innocent or first-time hearers of the term "Edmodo".

The second problem is with the impressions of the use of the Edmodo application after using it:

1. The Gloomy Outlook: along with the usage of the application in language learning, the respondents encountered the gloomy stage, where the hardship of trying something for the first time was experienced.
2. The Sanguine Perspective: this was popularized in the olden times as those people who love to talk and are everyone's friend. They are cheerleaders and seem like the happiest people in the world. They are "always a child" who needs to grow up. They have an appealing personality and love to communicate. They are known as lovers of creativity.

The third problem was with the significant uses of Edmodo in Language Learning: Language Learning Specs in Edmodo App: As a tool in language learning, the Edmodo Application may seem to be idealistic. Its specs are the following:

1. Technology Engager: while being dubbed as educators who can address the learning needs of the millennial and the cyber generations, educators nowadays are expected also to be knowledgeable about the things the learners use in coping with classroom instruction. Technology is one thing the world couldn't resist. It is because of its impact on the wild mind of humanity, and its possible strengths towards one's development.
2. Language Developer: The Edmodo application provides an environment for students who participate in the virtual classroom to collaborate and communicate.
3. Communication Enhancer: Edmodo Application is one thing the world couldn't resist. It is because of its impact on the wild mind of humanity, and its possible strengths towards one's development.

5. Conclusion

The current study approved that the Edmodo Application was overall successful for almost all CSS students in their language assessment. It became pleasurable, appreciated, and interesting.

1. Despite the different reactions or perceptions of the Grade 12 Senior High School Students, the first time Edmodo Application was introduced, it went to the acceptance of the application into language learning.
2. The use of the Edmodo Application changed the impressions of the Grade 12 Senior High School Students on its use in their language learning.
3. The significant uses of Edmodo in language learning provided an environment for students who participate in the virtual classroom to collaborate and communicate.

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